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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Benign anorectal diseases are commonly observed at all levels of healthcare and can greatly impact patients' quality of life. Both patients and healthcare providers often overlook and dismiss these conditions. However, prompt identification and appropriate treatment of these issues are essential for enhancing patients' comfort and well-being. Typical symptoms associated with anorectal diseases include alterations in bowel habits, discomfort, discharge, burning sensations, itching, and bleeding. In routine practice, conditions like hemorrhoids, anal fissures, anal fistulas, and perianal abscesses are frequently diagnosed. Many of these conditions can be accurately assessed through a thorough medical history and physical examination. Gathering a comprehensive history and conducting physical assessments are often as informative as more advanced diagnostic tools and can minimize the need for further testing in numerous patients (Cohee, Hurff, & Gazewood, 2020; Elagöz et al., 2023; Fargo & Latimer, 2012).

Materials and Methods: A narrative review was created for this review article after searching the Pubmed, Google Scholar, Medscape, and Uptodate databases.

Results: Anorectal disorders are characterized by pain, bleeding, itching, discharge, and discomfort. A diagnosis may typically be made and therapy initiated with anamnesis and physical examination after the patient's symptoms and related findings are thoroughly questioned. The only things that remain constant in anorectal disorders are dietary guidelines and lifestyle modifications. When patients apply to primary care, their doctors should advise them to avoid a sedentary lifestyle, develop healthy bathroom habits, and eliminate off spicy, acidic, and caffeine-containing substances from their diet (Cohee, Hurff, & Gazewood, 2020; Elagöz et al., 2023; Fargo & Latimer, 2012). About 40% of individuals with chronic anal fissures and the majority of patients with acute anal fissures heal with conservative and medical treatment (topical diltiazem, topical glyceryl trinitrate) (Menteş & Leventoğlu, 2011; Özdemir & Geçim, 2010; Zaghayan & Fleshner, 2011). Medical treatments (flavonoids, calcium dobesilate, topical local anesthetic, local corticosteroid, and local vasoconstrictor) are successful in treating acute symptoms, but interventional techniques remain the gold standard for treating hemorrhoidal disease and perianal fistula (Akçal et al., 2011; Geçim, 2011; Yüceyar, 2010). Compared to general surgeons, primary care physicians are more likely to treat pruritus ani (Markell & Billingham, 2010; Siddiqi & Siddika, 2018).

Conclusion: Due to feelings of embarrassment, patients often delay voicing their concerns. This can lead to the progression of treatable conditions into more severe forms. Consequently, the approach taken by primary care physicians is crucial. In order to manage anorectal complaints and make sure these conditions are successfully treated in their early phases; this study attempts to evaluate the healthcare solutions accessible in primary care.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Hemorrhoids, anal fistula, fissure, pruritus ani, anorectal

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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